

concentration of the rice plant with time may be explained by the plant's physiology during this period. In the first 4 days after transplanting, the roots were inactive. That might have limited the plant's water and nutrient absorption as reflected in the plants' withering, and yellowing, and their reduced nitrogen content. After 4 days, plant roots recovered from transplanting shock and regulated the water and nutrient supply. That condition was indicated by a return of greenness and increased nitrogen content in the plants. After 6 days, nitrogen was appropriated in the synthesis of metabolites and for fast plant growth. During this time the nitrogen supply probably was not commensurate with the rapid plant growth; thus the nitrogen content of the plants decreased sharply because of the "dilution effect."

To increase the efficiency of fertilizer use, it may be beneficial to apply nitrogen 5 days after transplanting. This

Effect of fungicide seed treatment on rice seedling growth

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The seedborne nature of sheath blight disease of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn has been established. Seeds of ADT3 1 were collected from sheath blight-affected fields, treated with test fungicides, and stored in polythene bags for 3 days. The test fungicides thiophanate, captafol, fenaminosulf, triarimol, PCNB, carbendazim, captan, chloroneb, carboxin, benomyl, triphenyltin acetate, Agrosan, thiram, oxycarboxin, MEMC, chlorothalonil were used at 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2% levels. The treated seeds were tested for germination, seedling growth, and vigor. Some treated seeds were stored for 8 months and then tested for viability.

Benomyl, chlorothalonil, and carboxin increased seed germination considerably over the control. Oxycarboxin, carboxin, chlorothalonil, and benomyl significantly increased shoot growth. Carbendazim,

Comparison of basal and delayed application of first dose of nitrogen on two rice cultivars. Ludhiana, India.

Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)	
	Palman 579	PR106
T ₁	5.4	6.4
T ₂	5.7	6.6

^a T₁ = 40 kg N/ha at transplanting + 40 kg N 3 wk after transplanting (WT) + 40 kg N 6 WT. T₂ = 40 kg N/ha at 7 days after transplanting + 40 kg N 3 WT + 40 kg N 6 WT.

observation is supported by results of a replicated field experiment conducted on Fatehpur loamy sand in the 1978 kharif (Jul-Oct) (see table).

The data show that application of nitrogen at 7 days after transplanting gave 0.3 t/ha more yield than its application at transplanting. Therefore, fertilizer use efficiency may be higher if the first dose of nitrogen is applied 5–7 days after transplanting. But further large-scale field testing in different environments is needed. ■

triarimol, captafol, thiram, oxycarboxin, chlorothalonil, benomyl, and captan at 0.2%) increased the root growth of rice seedlings. Seedlings from the treated seeds were more vigorous than the control. Seeds treated with oxycarboxin and MEMC maintained more than 90% seed viability after 8 months of storage. ■

Azolla manuring for rice

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In earlier trials Srinivasan and Pari showed that azolla incorporation 1 week before planting at 10, 20, and 30 t/ha (nitrogen levels as high as 100 kg/ha) gave yields equal to 25, 50, and 75 kg N/ha, respectively. They also found that growing azolla until harvest but without incorporation gave no beneficial effects.

Because the field cannot be kept fallow for growing azolla after the kuruvai harvest, it was decided to grow azolla among the planted crop and incorporate it after it covered the surface. Three replicated trials were laid out

during 1978 thaladi with inoculum levels of 1, 2, and 3 t/ha at nitrogen levels of 0 to 100 kg/ha in slabs of 25 kg. P₂O₅ and K₂O were uniformly applied at 50 kg/ha before planting. The test variety was IR20. Azolla was sown 1 week after planting; the water level was maintained at 5 cm. The inoculum levels at 1, 2, and 3 t/ha covered the field 55, 33, and 15 days after application, respectively. Azolla was incorporated after the water was drained.

In the trial where azolla inoculum was applied at 3 t/ha, a yield increase equal

Effect of azolla manuring on grain yield of rice. Aduthurai, India.

N levels (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha) at azolla inoculum level of		
	1 t/ha	2 t/ha	3 t/ha
0	2.9	2.8	2.9
0 + azolla	3.0	3.1	3.4
25	3.5	3.3	3.2
25 + azolla	3.5	3.5	3.6
50	3.6	3.5	3.1
50 + azolla	3.8	3.8	4.0
75	4.0	3.9	4.2
75 + azolla	4.1	4.0	4.6
100	4.4	4.3	4.7
100 + azolla	4.4	4.5	5.2
CD (P = 0.05%)	0.4	0.5	0.3

to that of 25 kg N/ha was observed (see table). In trials with inoculum levels of 1 and 2 t/ha there was no appreciable yield increase because of the delayed incorporation of azolla (62 and 40 days after planting, respectively). ■

Soil loss due to roguing in rice seed production plots

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The roguing of offtypes is a standard practice in pure seed production programs. The major roguing operation takes place after flowering. Uprooting the entire plant speeds the removal of rogues, but a considerable amount of topsoil sticking to the roots is also removed from the plot in the process.

We randomly sampled rogues uprooted from our rice seed-production plots,